

AIAL's Comments to the European Commission's Digital Omnibus (Digital Package on Simplification) Consultation

Date: 14th October 2025

Cite as: Harshvardhan J. Pandit (2025, October) "AIAL's Comments to the European Commission's Simplification – Digital Package and Omnibus Consultation" AI Accountability Lab (AIAL).

<https://aial.ie/research/policy/consultation-2025-EU-Digital-Omnibus-Simplification>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17352929

ABOUT AIAL

The AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) is a dedicated research lab within Trinity College Dublin that is focused on ensuring that the wider AI ecology — from research and product development, to regulation — centres public interest, particularly, the most marginalised and disenfranchised in society. Our inquiries into AI accountability, therefore, span from studies of large systems, structures, and ecologies (such as the AI field itself and regulatory processes) to executions of audits and evaluations on specific AI models, tools, and training datasets. We recognize that AI accountability research is most impactful when it can inform the public, impacted groups, and policy makers. Thus, we aim for active policy translation of our (as well as field wide) research.

You can find more information about the AIAL on its website at <https://aial.ie/>.

AUTHOR BIO

Dr. Harshvardhan Pandit is a Research Fellow in the AI Accountability Lab in Trinity College Dublin. His research interests are focused on solving real-world challenges associated with privacy, legal and regulatory compliance. Dr. Pandit is a nominated technical expert by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB). Dr. Pandit is also a member of the National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI), and through it participates within CEN/CENELEC and ISO groups on cybersecurity, privacy, and artificial intelligence, and is the co-editor for the ongoing ISO/IEC 27560 PII Processing Records standard. Additionally, Dr. Pandit also engages with standardisation activities in IEEE, in particular regarding P7012 machine-readable privacy terms, and in W3C as the chair of the W3C Data Privacy Vocabularies and Controls Community Group (DPVCG) that develops interoperable vocabularies for privacy and data protection activities based on legal and practical requirements.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	2
2. Concerns regarding lack of Impact Assessments.....	3
3. Questionable Efficacy of Diluting GDPR Article 30(5).....	4
4. Alternative Solutions without GDPR dilution.....	6
5. ePrivacy Directive and Cookies.....	10
6. AI Act.....	20

1. Introduction

This document represents the answers prepared by the team at AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) for the *European Commission's Simplification – Digital Package and Omnibus Consultation*¹, conducted by the European Commission as part of the lawmaking process. The consultation was open for 6 weeks from 16th September until 14th October 2025, during which the AIAL team submitted its response.

Regarding the scope and method of the omnibus proposal, AIAL has concerns regarding the justification of removing 'red tape' without a corresponding assessment of impacts to fundamental rights and freedoms. While the need for competitiveness is well understood, this lapse in typical rule making procedure is a severe risk to citizens as we increasingly see rights, especially those regarding digital services, healthcare, workers, and environment, are under threat owing to rapid technological proliferation. In this, the Commission's recent measures to increase the adoption of AI also risks creating new forms of surveillance, control, and violations at scale. This is the very reason the Commission initially proposed and has been able to successfully adopt the AI Act, which has placed a specific emphasis on AI systems considered as high-risk and established the world's first legal framework to address their harms to fundamental rights and freedoms. To now ignore these risks and their rapidly realising harms in the name of simplification would be a mistake and a step back for democratic processes that ensure citizen's interests.

Further, the Commission also has proposed removal of key documentation from regulatory measures regarding GDPR, as a means to simplify the regulatory burden. We show with empirical evidence how this creates a severe risk to the organisations' ability to address rights of the individual and also greatly lessens the degree of accountability

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14855-Simplification-digital-package-and-omnibus_en

present in the EU. This is highly likely to become an opportunity to further reduce the legal protections and to justify further dilution under the name of economic competitiveness. We therefore urge the Commission to avoid any reopening or dilution of the GDPR, and to instead focus on improved enforcement and simplification of compliance measures for organisations without changes to the GDPR.

In continuation of this, we also urge the Commission to not revoke fundamental protections regarding privacy afforded by the ePrivacy Directive. We welcome the resolve to address online consent popups and issues regarding cookies, but are concerned that the Commission is not addressing the underlying surveillance infrastructure that violates the privacy of citizens routinely and at massive scale. We therefore ask that the Commission directly address this core issue at source instead of tackling the symptoms (cookie banners). For this, we provide specific recommendations for how the Commission can utilise its proposed adoption of Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) in a way that works to uplift rights and freedoms of the individual without creating new risks and mechanisms for privacy violations.

In conclusion, we advocate for a cautious and pragmatic approach regarding any simplification as these directly affect fundamental rights and freedoms. While competitiveness is necessary, the Commission must support organisations in a way that advances rather than ignores fundamental rights from the onset. For this, we request the Commission to investigate other measures that reduce the effort of enforcement by supporting organisations with their compliance instead of focusing on reduction or dilution of regulations. Indeed, we feel that the EU can and should utilise its highly valued rights and freedoms as the very measures for measuring competitiveness and innovation, rather than focusing only on the artificially amalgamated metrics regarding its economy. We reiterate that a healthy and competitive EU is one where the competition comes from a high degree of assurance and accountability, and not where such measures can be easily sidelined for economic reasons.

2. Concerns regarding lack of Impact Assessments

We welcome the European Commission's attention and agenda regarding ensuring EU's competitiveness through relevant legal measures. We understand the backdrop of this as based in the findings of earlier reports, especially that by Draghi,² that have been used as a justification to reduce 'red tape' and improve competitiveness within the EU through 'simplification'. However, we are disturbed by the seemingly rapid proposals being put forth and moved through the rule making process without an impact assessment. The Commission's assertions that such proposals are only of a

² The future of European competitiveness: Report by Mario Draghi (2025) European Commission https://commission.europa.eu/topics/eu-competitiveness/draghi-report_en

technical nature are not supported with any evidence, especially an impact assessment, and are also at odds on its insistence that such measures are not expected to have negative impacts on the protection of fundamental rights.³

The impact assessment procedure in rule making is an important tool and part of the better regulation making framework.⁴ By not utilising it, the Commission has not ascertained with certainty that its proposals are indeed not affecting the aforementioned rights and interests of its Citizens. Additionally, the impact assessment is also an important aspect of the democratic nature of the rule making procedure as it enables citizens, and their elected representatives, to analyse the impacts of a legislative proposal and debate accordingly on whether to accept it. Without this supporting document, a drastic change to the existing laws as well as the future interpretation of yet to be enforced laws is difficult to justify as being safe and risk-averse, as the Commission has stated in more than one of its proposals.

Also concerning is how the Draghi report and the Commission's justification for competitiveness seems to focus only on increasing the use of data by organisations while reducing the documentation needed for legal compliance, and that this does not take into account how doing this might impact the rights and freedoms afforded by EU law to its citizens. We posit that in each law, such procedures are defined after an intense negotiation (the trialogue process), and that the resulting legal measure is still present because it is necessary for achieving the intended effects. If the Commission proposes to remove such a measure, even if only for SMEs and SMCs, then this still meets the bar to conduct an impact assessment under the Commission's own guidelines. We therefore request that this procedure be followed.

3. Questionable Efficacy of Diluting GDPR Article 30(5)

The text in this section has been adapted from the peer-reviewed publication titled "*Simple Now, Complex Later: The Questionable Efficacy of Diluting GDPR Article 30(5)*", which is scheduled to be presented later in October at the Annual Privacy Forum (APF), organised by ENISA and EU Commission's DG CNECT. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-07574-1_6

With the Draghi report as its justification, the Commission published a proposal on 21st May 2025 to amend the GDPR by extending the exception of Article 30(5) which currently covers SMEs as organisations with less than 250 employees, to also apply to SMCs as organisations with less than 750 employees. In its accompanying "legislative

³ Ares(2025)7724296 Call for evidence on Digital Omnibus (Digital Package on Simplification)

⁴ Impact assessments (last accessed: 2025) https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/impact-assessments_en

and financial digital statement" section notes the objection of this as reducing the administrative burdens and for simplified or assisted reporting. The Commission also notes that this is a new measure with unknown effectiveness. However, when we look at the legislative history, this is at least the third such exercise following the proposals and reviews of the Data Protection Directive and the GDPR. Additionally, the proposal also does not contain ANY monitoring and reporting rules for how the proposed measures will be assessed despite such measures already existing for the GDPR. We also note that such rules are necessary to be identified ahead of time to assess the suitability of the proposal. The proposal also does not provide any supporting impact assessment to justify that it will not result in an impact to rights and freedoms. We therefore consider this sufficient to raise questions as to whether this proposal has been rushed without taking these important steps.

In order to better understand this proposal, we analysed the proposed amendments to the GDPR and whether they will indeed support the SMEs and SMCs as intended in the Commission's outlined objectives. In particular, we focused on the increased exceptions for SMEs and SMCs under GDPR Article 30(5) regarding Records of Processing Activities (ROPA). We found that the exception appears beneficial as written and in conjunction with Recital 13, but is effectively redundant in practice as the effort intended to be prevented is still required to meet other GDPR obligations. We also found that by removing the obligation to maintain documentation the Commission is promoting an organisational culture of weakened accountability, lack of oversight, and deviating from established data governance principles and that this risks compliance with other GDPR obligations. If the intended impact is to ease the regulatory burdens for SMEs and SMCs, then this proposal will, to put it plainly, *'cut corners now and court problems later'*.

By proposing the GDPR Article 30(5) derogation be extended to even more organisations, the benefits remain small, but the risk of organisations not being prepared grows larger without any real benefit. The fallout from this will also extend beyond the organisations themselves as supervisory authorities rely on the organisations to provide them information on their processing activities. Currently, they rely on ROPA as the first step in understanding the activities of the organisation, and a badly maintained ROPA is an immediate symptom of bad governance practices within the organisation or an intentional misdirection from the organisation, either of which raise alarms regarding their GDPR compliance.

By removing the requirement for ROPA from more organisations, the investigating process is likely to take more time as authorities have to request information and organisations have to expend time and effort to prepare it, and there is likely to be a back-and-forth exchange of information in this process which further expends time and resources. Additionally, the existing decisions and case law regarding GDPR also

underscore how the Article 30 obligations are inherently tied to compliance issues with other Articles. To date, there is only one instance (available publicly) where a fine was issued solely for a violation involving a ROPA. Decisions referencing the Article 30 provisions are always accompanied by violations of other articles – which means Article 30 violations are symptoms of other underlying and manifested problems. This is known to practitioners and also why the ROPA is considered a key accountability artefact. Information being missing, incorrect, or incomplete in the ROPA makes it highly likely there is also something wrong with the other obligations, and therefore also makes it an essential data governance tool for compliance.

To conclude, the Commission's current proposal should be revised due to its lack of practical usefulness and the high probability that it encourages practices that risk liability and compliance for the organisations it intends to support and promote. It is in effect a limited dilution of the GDPR as it reduces the obligations for a specific group of organisations. The justification for this is absent from the proposal, there has been no impact assessment conducted regarding validity of measures, and further – and most importantly – we question whether it will actually lead to the intended outcomes.

4. Alternative Solutions without GDPR dilution

In the peer reviewed article, referenced at the start of this section, we propose several alternatives that will allow the Commission to achieve its intended effect without the dilution of the GDPR. In fact, we strongly oppose any reopening of the GDPR, and by extension the other *data aquis* regulations as these are yet to be completely implemented and are yet to be enforced. However, by withdrawing their requirements at this stage, the Commission risks undoing the strategic implementation of these rules as envisioned in the digital decade program, and also as these rules form the basis for other regulations. This thus risks creating a domino effect that cascades compliance and enforcement issues across regulations. We again urge the Commission to consider undertaking an impact assessment for such proposals in order to ensure rights and freedoms are not affected.

Supporting Authorities

We also note that in most cases, the enforcement of GDPR has suffered for years from an under-resourcing of supervisory authorities. Therefore, we suggest empowering the authorities as a key step to ensure simplification. With better resourcing, the authorities will be in a position to provide better guidance, governance, and resources, which have been established as necessary for SMEs. By creating new rules, the Commission is also increasing the burden of these authorities as they must now revise all of their resources and guidelines, and must again pause enforcement to "explain" the new rules to organisations. Instead, the Commission should be encouraging measures that simplify access to rights and accountability. For this, the support of

technical mechanisms to help organisations, citizens, and authorities is necessary in the 21st century. We point to the digitalisation of tax filing regulations as the best examples for how consistent resources can simplify procedures for organisations and citizens alike. This is done without a dilution of either obligations or a reduction of documentation. Instead, the increased automation provides a greater degree of possibility to implement regulations, and to have greater use of information to ensure compliance through accountability, which ultimately benefits the rights of both organisations and people.

Extending utility of Certifications

Another avenue for simplification without dilution is to extend the Commission's proposal to expand the scope of codes of conducts and certifications under GDPR to also take into account sectorial 'patterns of commonalities'. Through this, the Commission should encourage development of effective frameworks through which SMEs and SMCs can be assured of their GDPR compliance practices. In this manner, the focus will always be on the irregularities and the activities that fall outside the 'known' spheres of compliance, and thus promote regulatory learnings and requirements for further regulations like the AI Act. Taking such a measure will provide support and assurance to the many SMEs and SMCs who are subjected to the GDPR because they involve personal data in the course of activities such as HR or typical customer and marketing activities, for which common resources can be collectively developed and provided at the EU rather than Member State levels both as a way to pool resources and to avoid fragmentation.

Ensuring compliance solutions are themselves compliant

The GDPR led to the practice of organisations utilising external platforms and services to manage their compliance (referred to as Compliance Management Platforms or CMPs), where such CMPs promise fully compliant solutions that the SMEs and SMCs perceive as being a quick way to meet their obligations. However, such organisations often do not act in the best interests of their clients and act like liabilities in disguise. For example, 'common market practices' adopted based on compliance claims have been shown to be severely problematic regarding consent management and other functionalities. By not addressing these issues of real-world power dynamics, and instead focusing on simplification, organisations will continue to pretend they are compliant under a mistaken or a wilfully ignorant perspective. To remedy this, the Commission's proposals to revitalise the use of codes of conduct as per GDPR Article 40 and certifications as per Article 42 should also focus on the tools and vendors used by SMEs and SMCs to achieve compliance and to avoid misleading and bad compliance practices. In essence, SMEs and SMCs should be able to 'trust' compliance solutions and their providers.

Ensuring alignment between GDPR and the AI Act

Take the example of a newly formed SME/SMC that focuses on AI technologies using personal data – it must not only take in to account the GDPR, but also now the AI Act, and where these are not designed to be ‘complied with’ together despite being ‘authored’ by the same governance system. Though the AI Act references GDPR as being applicable regarding processing of personal data, it does not go beyond this ‘simple’ acknowledgement. This means organisations and authorities face a common burden of figuring out how to comply with the AI Act and how to reuse GDPR compliance to avoid duplication of efforts. The drafting of the laws does not facilitate this process, and the fragmentation of rules across EU/EEA Member States further complicates it.

Our analysis, titled "Impact Assessment Requirements in the GDPR vs the AI Act: Overlaps, Divergence, and Implications",⁵ shows how DPIA requirements are so fragmented across Member States that there is no clarity or certainty on its complementary status with the FRIA in AI Act Article 27(4), and that the GDPR’s roles of controller and processor are not accounted for in the AI Act despite there being a significant scope of AI systems processing personal data somewhere along their lifecycle and high-risk AI systems dominantly involving such processing. It is highly expected that organisations that already address the GDPR are also interested in using AI technologies and will thus have to consider the AI Act. If instead, the AI Act was written in a way that would offer such organisations a natural progression from their existing processes and obligations to include AI, it would have been more useful than the current duplication of individual and national efforts on this topic. In particular, GDPR authorities must now expend considerable time and resources to understand and provide guidance and resources based on combining the GDPR with the AI Act.

If the AI Act had been published in such a manner where it specifically and directly updated the requirements of the GDPR where AI systems utilise personal data, SMEs and SMCs would have received a consistent and harmonised set of requirements to maintain records in the same document and format with some information coming from the GDPR and some from the AI Act. At the same time, the GDPR would have benefitted from the AI Act’s comprehensive coverage of ‘automated’ systems, particularly in context of Article 22 and the right to object to decision-making, while also paving the way to regulate development of recent rapid developments such as generative AI models and AI agents, which also heavily involve personal data, by reusing the established Article 6 legal bases and the transparency, access, and objection rights outlined in Articles 12–23. Such harmonisations are necessary to reduce the ‘friction’ between regulations as GDPR’s purpose limitations are intended to limit processing whereas the AI Act also wants to stimulate AI development.

⁵ <https://osf.io/preprints/osf/6qhzi>

Utilise RegTech and eGov Technologies

A common ‘compliance platform’ is an excellent way to support maintaining documentation where the system utilises advances in information management to avoid manual laborious processes for both the organisation and the authority. Its feasibility, especially within economic constraints, can be studied from success stories like the Jamaican Data Protection Act in 2020 which required the assigned Commissioner to develop such a notification system for organisations to register their activities. Since organisations under the GDPR are effectively required to publicly publish information due to Articles 13 and 14, this is not an additional burden as the same system can also assist in the creation of privacy notices for these articles. Notably, the Jamaican implementation utilises common ‘patterns’ or ‘use-cases’, such as HR, marketing, and account creation, identified through a detailed consultation process. These allow the organisation to express its intended activity with a guided and controlled vocabulary that is backed by a machine-readable interoperable format (see below) to produce documentation on both ends, thus benefiting the organisation and providing authorities with audit-ready information without duplication of efforts. Without such a ‘technologically effective’ solution, sustaining and succeeding is difficult for the increasing amount of regulations and organisational processes, especially for future visions such as Data Spaces. Such approaches are already used in the eProcurement system for EU public procurement, and are thus not out of place in the EU’s legal toolkit. The recent call to support the AI Office also involves producing software to aid the enforcement of the AI Act. And the EU Council also agrees with this approach by noting measures such as a centralised glossary, harmonised and pre-filled templates, and targeted open source ‘kits’ and ‘forms’ for SMEs.

For SMEs and SMCs, this would be a boon as most of their current GDPR implementations would thus be offloaded to automated software that is backed by the authority, thereby reducing the effective reporting requirements and also providing them with legal clarity and support as needed. The effort required to produce such a system is not disproportionate to the benefits it will provide, and can be offset by developing a common system across EU (which incidentally will also help the one-stop-shop system), with registration fees as done in Jamaica and in the UK, and through the fines collected under the GDPR. It will also help streamline the rights exercise requests, assist in breach reporting – including cross-regulation incident reporting, and allow authorities to provide targeted support to struggling organisations at scale through the use of consistent automation. This is what we envision as actual simplification – something that assures a high degree of accountability and compliance without compromising on the law or the rights.

The potential of this approach also aligns well with the Commission’s Horizon research programme, particularly under Cluster 4 for use of data and AI technologies for

compliance. This gives another possibility for the feasibility of proposed approaches through fiscal co-ordination, e.g., between the research programs and between authorities. Such avenues should be further explored and used to rapidly exploit research results and to consolidate existing efforts into a useful solutions that also promote further competitiveness through innovation for achieving compliance.

5. ePrivacy Directive and Cookies

We support the Commission's agenda for streamlining online experiences and addressing consent fatigue. However we are concerned that this might result in an increased violation of the individual's privacy as any mechanism used to justify collection and processing of personal data would carry risks of enabling this without the user's consent. We therefore focus exclusively on supporting the user to prevent and halt such processing through the use of Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) and to prevent unwanted third parties from exploiting the user's data and relationship with a service provider through the use of such PETs.

Our rationale for this stance is that the online experience is severely broken where individuals' browsing the internet or using apps on their personal devices are constantly harassed with consent requests and excessive sharing of personal data with a large number of unknown third parties. Even though this has been repeatedly shown to constitute illegal practices as these parties create mass profiling based on tracking the individuals across websites, enforcement has been slow due to the sheer scale of these activities and their near-ubiquity in all internet-enabled services. We therefore reject any call or measure that increases the availability of data to any organisation while such practices are not only occurring, but are so widespread so as to be considered the norm on the internet. Only when such mass invasions and violations of our fundamental right to privacy are stopped, can any measure be trusted to facilitate the data for the benefit of both the individual and the service provider.

We note that consent is the cornerstone of EU data protection regulations, and a right enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights. In order for consent to be a mechanism for individual empowerment and freedom, as envisioned in the Charter, the problematic misuses of consent must be stopped without detriment to the rights of the individual or organisations' legitimate privacy-respecting activities. In order to achieve this, it is vital that technical solutions are identified that reduce not only the burden on individuals to manage their privacy, but also support legal enforcement by making it simple to determine compliance. We acknowledge candidates as Global

Privacy Control (GPC)⁶ and Advanced Data Protection Control (ADPC)⁷ and note that we do not believe either of them are suitable to adopt in their current state.⁸

We therefore suggest the Commission identify specific candidates for such technical solutions, and support this by listing requirements which must be afforded via law in order to make effective use of such solutions to address the aforementioned problems.

Determination of Valid Automation Signals

[1] The determination of whether an automated signal is a valid technical means to exercise the data subject's rights must also ensure its consistent interpretation and application across the EU.

Rationale: In order to determine whether a signal should be legally accepted as enforceable, it must have an authority declaring it as such. In order to ensure consistency and harmonisation, this decision must be consistent across the EU. Naturally, this means the EDPB should determine and issue guidelines as its opinions are binding on all Member States.

[2] Where an automated signal is being assessed for use to convey the data subject's decisions regarding processing of their personal data, the criteria for evaluating the signal must include whether the scope, roles, and effects of the signal are aligned with the GDPR, in particular regarding the data subject's rights.

Rationale: The assessment of the signal to be legally enforceable must consist of its interpretation under the GDPR and its acceptance must be an indication of its validity as being compatible and enforceable under the GDPR.

Signals that are assessed to be valid in this manner are referred to as "accepted automated signals" in the subsequent recommendations.

Role of Signals Regarding Consent

[3] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey a consent decision to prevent processing of their personal data, and where they communicate such

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/gpc/>

⁷ <https://www.dataprotectioncontrol.org/spec/>

⁸ Data Protection and Consenting Communication Mechanisms: Current Open Proposals and Challenges (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1109/EuroSPW55150.2022.00029>

decisions prior to a consent request, data controllers must respect the decision and must not present the data subject with a consent request.

Rationale: Data subjects get too many popups, leading to frustration and consent fatigue. If the data subject has already decided to refuse the processing, and therefore is going to click on the Refuse or Disagree button in the consent interface, then there is no need to show them the request if the signal is already communicating this information. By contrast, if the data subject did not have such a signal, then the controller may continue to request their consent. In this, we note that there are no further risks to the data subject as the signal is NOT indicating that the data subject is permitting processing based on consent without the need for a notice or request.

[4] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey a decision to prevent processing of their personal data, the data subject must not be made to interact with a notice or interface solely for the purposes of providing information relevant to making a decision, such as that pursuant to Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR, as they have already expressed their wishes. As this information is also needed to meet the GDPR transparency obligations, the controller must make it available through other means, such as within privacy policies, without detriment to the data subject's experience of using the service.

Rationale: The popups are also used to communicate information at the first instance of the data subject's visit to the website or app. However, for consent, such information is of no consequence if the data subject has made a decision to not permit the processing even before reaching the website. The signal communicates exactly such an intent, and therefore if the data subject still wishes to obtain this information, they can do so by going to the privacy policy. There is no need for a popup here as it only serves to degrade the user's experience of the service as the user has already made a decision to not permit processing.

[5] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey the decision to prevent processing of their personal data, and where the signal is conveyed within the same context as the data subject's consent for the same processing, the consent shall be considered ambiguous and invalid.

Rationale: This is to ensure that there is no loophole in the use of signals or that controllers continue to harass users with popups. If a signal is used to communicate the data subject's decision to not give consent and to thus prevent the processing, the controller may still try to obtain such consent by again showing the popup and inducing

the user to click yes (as is the current scenario). If this is allowed, the use of signals will diminish, and we will again get the same issues with too many popups and consent fatigue. Therefore, if such a case arises, and the data subject accidentally or through being manipulated clicks on the agree button, this requirement protects them by explicitly identifying the ambiguity between the signal that prevents processing and the data subject's action which seems to permit it. Under GDPR, this cannot be considered an unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes. Note, we explicitly reject the notion of the data subject's manual action overriding the automated signal, as this would defeat the very purpose of an automated signal if manual actions must still be taken regarding it. Instead, the ambiguity here can only be resolved by the signal being turned off and then the data subject giving consent. We address this in a later requirement.

[6] The data subject shall have a 'Right to not be disturbed' under which an automated signal used to convey the data subject's decision to prevent processing of their personal data must result in no further notice to be given and no further decisions to be required from the data subject.

Rationale: As explained earlier, controllers or third parties may wish to manipulate the user into making a decision through popups that request, nudge, or otherwise seek to influence the user into changing the decision already communicated through their automated signal. To prevent such 'harassment', we recommend an explicit right that prevents disturbance to the user, similar to how we have controls over unsolicited junk mail. Without such a right, users may continue seeing popups and being asked to make decisions even though they have already communicated their wishes through the automated signal.

[7] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to exercise the right to withdraw consent in accordance with Article 7(3) of the GDPR, the controller must interpret it as if the data subject had manually withdrawn their consent.

Rationale: This makes sure that the automated signal has the intended effect, and that there is no loophole where the controller uses a popup to ensure the data subject indeed wants to withdraw consent and in doing so also requests the data subject to not withdraw their consent. This will result in popups everywhere again as controllers will keep asking not to withdraw. The recommendation therefore relies on withdrawal of consent, as per Article 7(3), to have the intended effect without an opportunity to manipulate the individual.

[8] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to exercise the right to withdraw consent in accordance with Article 7(3) of the GDPR, the controller must implement the withdrawal without undue delay.

Rationale: This ensures that there are no delays in the implementation, and it is currently also the interpretation of consent withdrawal under the GDPR which must be applied immediately and without undue delay.

[9] Where an accepted automated signal is used to exercise the data subject's right to withdraw consent in accordance with Article 7(3) of the GDPR, the data subject's decision must be respected without further consent requests as long as the signal is in effect.

Rationale: As explained before, upon withdrawal of consent, the controller may seek an opportunity to again ask for consent. This could be immediately upon withdrawal or soon thereafter. This means more popups to the user, and the recommendation makes sure that this is not allowed to take place. If the data subject withdraws consent through the automated signal, and continues to indicate such prevention through the signal, then it is clear that the data subject does not wish to permit such processing. Therefore, it is pointless to ask them to reconsider via another popup or consent request.

[10] Where a data subject uses an accepted automated signal to exercise the right to withdraw consent in accordance with Article 7(3) of the GDPR, and where the consent involves sharing or transfer of personal data to third parties, the controller must inform each third party of the withdrawal without undue delay to ensure the restriction of processing

Rationale: In the online context, the involvement of third parties is disturbingly common, especially for tracking and profiling in behavioural/surveillance advertising. When the data subject uses an automated signal, they are relying on the technical means of their device or app to ensure their decisions are communicated to all relevant parties. This recommendation creates this same obligation on the controller to ensure that the data subject's withdrawal has the intended effect by explicitly requiring the withdrawal to also be communicated to all third parties who are processing personal data based on the data subject's consent. This is aligned with the similar obligation regarding objection to legitimate interests referred to in Article 19 of the GDPR. Without this, the data subject will be required to undertake a massive and unfairly

complex effort to track down each third party and express their decision to prevent processing.

Scope of Signals

[11] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey a consent decision to prevent processing of their personal data, the scope of this decision may be broad such that many processing activities are covered by it. Data controllers must interpret such a broad decision as the data subject indicating their decision to not permit the specific processing.

Rationale: This is necessary as each controller's purposes may be considered unique, and that it would be unfair to ask the data subject to configure their automated signal for each such unique purpose as this would be as much if not more cumbersome than manually expressing their decision to the controller. Instead, the utility of technical signals is that they allow the data subject to communicate a decision over a broad range without manually configuring each decision. For example, the GPC signal allows data subjects to indicate, broadly, that they do not wish to consent to permit any processing where personal data is shared with third parties. The ADPC signal similarly has a flexible structure where the data subject can express their decision to prevent processing for a broad range of purposes, including all and any. If such broad signals are not accepted, then the data subject will be forced to interact with popups and other such notices, which will not be fair to them as they already have made a decision to not accept such processing. We think of this as a similar right available to consumers to not enter the premises of a shop as a broad decision to not purchase anything, whereas if they do wish to purchase something then they must make a specific choice.

[12] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey a decision to prevent processing of their personal data, and the decision applies to more than one processing activity within the same request, data controllers must interpret it as the data subject individually expressing their decision to refuse each processing activity.

Rationale: Similar to the earlier rationale, a broad signal provides a greater utility and practicality for the data subject. For controllers, this can also be useful as they frequently provide a single interface or popup to request multiple consent decisions. If the data subject's automated signal indicates that the data subject does not want to permit any of these processing, then it is clear from the signal. Therefore, in such cases, the popup will not be shown for any of those purposes.

[13] Where a data subject uses an automated signal is to convey the decision to

prevent processing of their personal data, the signal's effects must be implemented across all devices, mediums, applications, and contexts without requiring the data subject to repeat their wishes for each of them

Rationale: This recommendation is necessary as data subjects access online services from many different contexts and terminal devices. If the signal is accepted only in one situation, then the data subject must now take additional effort in other contexts to enforce the same decisions over and over again. This is detrimental to their experience, and is also cumbersome for organisations as they now have a conflict between the different decisions. Therefore, where the controller knows the identity of the data subject, and the automated signal indicates some processing is prevented, this should be implemented in all contexts as is already required under the GDPR. This is without prejudice to a technical signal or setting restricting its scope to a particular device or app, in which case, this recommendation does not need to be applied.

Safeguarding Data Subject's Right to Use Signals

[14] A controller or a third party is prohibited from interfering with the data subject's independence to configure and express their decisions through an automated signal. Such interference must mean the data subject's consent or non-objection is invalid.

Rationale: This recommendation is essential to explicitly cover the situation explained earlier where the controller may attempt to subvert the automated signal by asking the data subject to change their signal or otherwise make a different decision. This would be interference in the data subject's ability to make a free decision, and therefore should be prevented. If such interference occurs in the context of consent, it is already considered as leading to invalid consent due to the violation of the 'freely given' requirement.

[15] Where a controller or third party fails to receive or otherwise implement an automated signal, it must communicate this to the data subject without undue delay. Such failure cannot be used as a valid legal basis for processing based on the non-existence of the signal, and cannot be used as a substitute to ignore the signal or its effects.

Rationale: This recommendation covers the potential loophole where a controller may attempt to subvert the automated signal by claiming that they cannot implement it. The principle of legal enforceability, which an 'accepted automated signal' must possess, is based on the necessity to implement it. Therefore, this recommendation makes it clear that such excuses should not be used to justify processing of personal

data, or as a reason to claim ignorance or inability to comply with the automated signal's effects.

[16] Where an accepted automated signal is used to convey the data subject's decision to prevent processing of their personal data for a specific criteria, the decision must apply to all subsequent processing that meets the criteria even if such criteria are not present at the time of the decision.

Rationale: This recommendation refers to the situation where a controller may claim that an automated signal does not apply because the said processing is not 'occurring' at that precise moment. However, GDPR does not distinguish between processing occurring at the time of requesting consent or objection, and instead allows the data subject to make a decision regarding processing that may also take place in the future. Therefore, this recommendation makes sure that the decision communicated by the automated signal is also interpreted in a manner that is consistent with this effect under GDPR. For example, the GPC signal prevents sharing data with third parties, and if this is not taking place currently but may take place in the future, then the decision to not share data also applies in the future. The recommendation attempts to ensure this effect by requiring the controller to apply the signal's criteria to all subsequent processing, and to implement its effects for any processing that satisfies the criteria.

[17] Inclusion or incorporation of automated signals within notices and consenting interfaces that prevent the data subject from access to a service or force a decision are prohibited.

Rationale: This recommendation ensures that the data subjects are not forced to confirm the decision again and again in a manual capacity as this would defeat the utility of using an automated signal. By requiring the data subject to manually express the decision again, there is potential for mischief, as also explained earlier, where the controller may attempt to subvert the data subject's choice and coerce or manipulate them into making a different decision. The recommendation makes sure that such practices are prevented. This is necessary to ensure that the data subject enjoys the benefits of automation in their decisions, and also for the website to not be required to show notices or popups which improves their user experience. If the decisions communicated by an automated signal are integrated within a popup, then it means the popup would still be shown to the user to request consent. If the user gives consent through such a popup while the signal is active, this leads to ambiguous consent and also increases the potential use of manipulative techniques or dark patterns to achieve this. We already see this occurring at large scales in popups regarding online tracking based advertising. This is also discussed elsewhere as the justification for why the data

subject needs a 'right to not be disturbed' unless the exception for being low-risk applies, which surveillance advertising clearly does not.

Balancing Controller's Rights with Privacy of the Data Subject

[18] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey the decision to prevent processing of their personal data, and where the scope of the decision is sufficiently broad such that it applies to multiple purposes, the controller may request the data subject for an exception to the decision for a specific purpose. This exception must only for a limited duration, and must only be asked for processing that does not involve risks to the data subject. The exception must exclude profiling, automated decision making, and marketing (including advertising). If the data subject agrees to the exception, this must not be interpreted as the data subject's consent to the specified processing. In order for the exception to apply, there must be an unambiguous indication of the data subject's agreement that does not conflict with any decision sent by their automated signal.

Rationale: While the earlier recommendations focused solely on the data subject and their protection and convenience, this recommendation ensures that legitimate business and organisational practices are also balanced in the use of automated signals that prevent processing of personal data. In this case, the recommendation allows controllers to request an exception, but only where the processing is not going to result in risks to the data subject. To make this explicit, the recommendation lists tracking and profiling as not being applicable for the exception as these are clearly detrimental to the data subject's privacy, and also the reason why they require additional considerations under the GDPR. If the controller does not engage in such risky practices, and there are no third parties as the controller does not have any control over their activities, then it is safe to assume that there are no inherent risks to the data subject. Therefore, the controller is allowed to request an exception. The recommendation makes it clear that if such an exception is granted, it does not constitute as valid consent, as the exception is only regarding the use of automated signals, and that the controller must still request and obtain valid consent as per the GDPR. The recommendation also clarifies that for the exception to apply the data subject must stop sending the automated signal to the controller, as otherwise there will be ambiguity with conflicting decisions from the data subject and the automated signal. The data subject can stop such signals for a specific website or app through the relevant settings of their web browser or device. The length of the recommendation is a necessity to ensure that businesses have an ability to engage with the data subject and request their consent if really needed, but that such a mechanism does not become an avenue to create friction with popups or malpractices for the data subject.

[19] Where analytics or other measurements are performed solely by the controller based on a valid legitimate interest under the GDPR, and where there is no tracking or profiling of the data subject, and where there is no involvement of third parties, then such processing activities should be exempted from the requirement to obtain the data subject's consent as required under Article 5(3) ePrivacy Directive

Rationale: This recommendation targets the requirement for the ePrivacy Directive to obtain consent, and its resulting implementations as cookie banners. Where the other recommendations remove the need for popups, the ePrivacy Directive may still necessitate a popup to inform the users about cookies and request consent for their use. To remedy this, it is important to note that GDPR already has a high bar for what is considered a valid legitimate interest, i.e. where there is no risk to the data subject and this has been confirmed through the proportionality assessment. If such uses involve cookies or other ePD regulated storage mechanisms, and there is no tracking or profiling as these are considered risky to the data subject as per the previous explanations, then there is a very low risk to the data subject. [CNIL has a similar interpretation](#), but because of the jurisdictional scope of French data protection regulation, this recommendation is seeking to have a similar interpretation be consistently applied at the EU level.

Objection to Legitimate Interests

[20] The determination of whether an automated signal is accepted as a valid technical means to exercise the data subject's right to object referred to in Article 21(5) GDPR must take into account whether the signal can introduce risks to the data subject by permitting processing through the same signal. Where such risks outweigh the benefits of using the signal, the signal must not be considered as valid.

Rationale: The GDPR already envisions objection to the use of legitimate interests through technical means, which here is achieved through the automated signal. However, in order for such signals to be enforceable, they need to be formally approved (as explained earlier). As part of this assessment, it is vital to assess whether the mechanisms for objecting can also be used to manipulate the data subject in expressing a permission or to withdraw their objection in a manner that results in excess processing of their personal data. This creates a risk to the rights of the data subject, in particular regarding protection of their personal data. Therefore, where such automated signals are used to communicate objections under Article 21(5), they must not simultaneously permit other processing based on the same signal.

[21] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey their objection under Article 21(5) of the GDPR, the objection must be further communicated to each recipient as required under Article 18(1)(d) of the GDPR without undue delay.

Rationale: This ensures that the objections expressed via an automated signal are correctly interpreted in accordance with the GDPR. If the objections are regarding processing involving third parties or other recipients, then the controller must communicate this objection to each recipient in accordance with Article 18(1)(d). The recommendation ensures that this obligation is explicit to the controller as also applicable when the data subject uses an automated signal to exercise the objection. The controller now also has the choice to use the same automated signal to inform such recipients, though this is not necessary for compliance as the controller may also utilise other means to achieve the same.

[22] Where a data subject uses an automated signal to convey their objection under Article 21(5) of the GDPR, the data subject must not be forced to further interact with notices or requests regarding the restricted processing

Rationale: This recommendation ensures that there are no detrimental experiences for the data subject when they object to processing under Article 21(5). Since the GDPR does not explicitly make it clear, there is a potential for the controller to simply ask the data subject to reconsider, or to delay their decision, or to consent to this processing instead. Since this can also be used as a means to manipulate the data subject into making such a decision, the recommendation seeks to prevent such practices from materialising. This is in alignment with similar issues regarding refusing or withdrawing consent using an automated signal with the recommendation preventing further interactions with the data subject so as to respect their decisions. Broadly, this recommendation is also necessary to implement the 'right to not be disturbed' mentioned before.

Acknowledgements: We thank the following people for their thoughts regarding the section on ePrivacy Directive and Cookies recommendations:

- Prof. Frederik J. Zuiderveen Borgesius (ICT and Law, iHub, Radboud University)
- Prof. Nataliia Bielova (Research Director, PRIVATICS, Inria)
- Prof. Dr. Cristiana Teixeira Santos (Law, Economics and Governance, Utrecht University; Nominated Technical Expert EDPB)
- Prof. Sebastian Zimmeck (Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Wesleyan University)
- Robin Berjon (Deputy director, IPFS Foundation)

6. AI Act

As the Commission is yet to publish any concrete proposal regarding modifications to the AI Act, we share our caution in advance of such proposals as the AI Act's implementation is only starting. Given that one of the primary intentions of the AI Act is to ensure fundamental rights are not harmed through the use of AI, it is yet to be fully developed and deployed. In fact, we point to the current lack of fundamental right toolkits necessary for the AI Act as well as their delays regarding the harmonised standards as evidence that the AI Act is yet to be fully established. Once this is done, the AI Act will act as the primary regulation to identify, address, and create accountability for AI systems that have the risk to cause harm or actually cause harmful incidents to materialise. In addition, the provisions of the AI Act are also intended to increase transparency regarding the use of AI and its recognition and impacts on individuals. In this manner, the AI Act is a necessary regulation for the accountability of increasing AI uses, and a necessary tool to ensure technologies comply with EU fundamental rights and freedoms. Therefore, we express a strong opinion that delaying or diluting the AI Act's intended protections risks creating uncertainty in the implementation and also reduces the protection of fundamental rights.

In light of the stated agenda for harmonisation of regulations, we also note the significant overlap between the AI Act and the GDPR when considering the high-risk categorisations of AI Systems in Annex III. As our analysis has shown,⁹ most of the high-risk cases in the AI Act's Annex III require a DPIA under GDPR. The analysis also shows how the DPIA requirements vary by Member States, and that this creates a fragmented set of rules for AI systems to follow regarding GDPR. We request the Commission to identify and support such inter-regulatory procedures to ensure organisations have the necessary clarity and support needed to respect and uphold rights through impact assessments. We also request the Commission to provide similar support and resources to the implementers of the GDPR and AI Act respectively so that they can effectively co-operate to provide relevant guidance, and can enforce issues as they arise together. For us, this would amount to a better simplification agenda as it would provide clarity in the market regarding how to make responsible use of AI.

We are also concerned that the Commission's strategies regarding AI seem overly focused only on increasing the uptake of AI. And that this risks sidelining GDPR enforcement in a rush to create more training data by exploiting personal data without consideration of the protections and rights established under the GDPR. We are also concerned that the rising uptake of AI means also a corresponding increase in the potential harms through misuse of AI, especially where AI is used to make unscientific, baseless, and phrenological assessments of the individual without their active participation, or consent, or awareness. The GDPR's intended protections against this,

⁹ Impact Assessment Requirements in the GDPR vs the AI Act: Overlaps, Divergence, and Implications (2025) <https://osf.io/preprints/osf/6qhzj>

whether through special categories or automated decision making, need to be strictly interpreted to further strengthen and simplify the AI Act's implementation. Otherwise we may end up facing a rapid decrease in our rights and freedoms as AI technologies get used at scale while diminishing our rights with every use.

~ END ~